

Where do synthetic respondents take consumer research?

58th TRC meeting in Faro (Portugal), April 2026

Dirk Schmücker, NIT, Kiel

Warning!

This is a new and dynamically
developing field of research.

Please do not expect absolute truths.

Agenda

Daniel Starch (1883–1979)

> 100 years ago

Psychologist

1920–1926 Professor at Harvard

1923–1973 „Daniel Starch and staff“ marketing research firm

Developer of the **Starch test** (ad recognition)

Publications:

Advertising: Its Principles, Practice, and Technique (1914)

Principles of Advertising (1923)

Research Methods in Advertising (1923)

Picture taken from: Borden, N. H. (1957). Daniel Starch. *Journal of Marketing*, 21(3), 265. <https://doi.org/10.2307/1247515>

What consumer researchers did over the last 100 years or so

Observe

Ask questions

Picture of Bronislaw Malinowski with natives on Trobriand Islands, ca 1918, via Wikimedia Commons.

Survey data collection process times

Own estimate für ~ 500 respondents, ~ 10 minutes

Productivity kills quality

See for example: Lohmann, M., & Schmücker, D. (2009). Internet research differs from research on internet users: Some methodological insights into online travel research. *Tourism Review*, 64(1), 32–47. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1108/16605370910948849>

Agenda

1

What consumer researchers did over the last 100 years or so

2

What happened since 2022

3

Two examples for the state of the play

4

What can be expected in the years to come?

Where generative AI can assist consumer researchers

Daniel F. Galouye

Simulacron-3

or

Counterfeit World

Adaptations

Rainer Werner Fassbinder: **Welt am Draht** (1973)
Josef Rusnak: **The Thirteenth Floor** (1999)
Laurence & Andrew Wachowski: **The Matrix** (1999)
Jay Scheib: **World of Wires** (2012)

Biography

Daniel Francis Galouye was born in February 1920 in New Orleans. He worked as a reporter for several newspapers until his retirement in 1967. As an author, he published five novels, among them Simulacron-3, and a larger number of short stories. Galouye passed away in September 1976 in his hometown New Orleans.

First published 1964 by Bantam Books, New York.

This edition designed and edited
by Dirk Schmücker, 2025

Typeset with Adobe Source Sans/Serif

Where generative AI can assist consumer researchers

* Generative Agents, Silicon Samples, Digital Twins, ...

Cian Murphy • 3rd+
Co Managing Director at nfpResearch
1d • 🌐

+ Follow ...

Nate Silver on using "synthetic data" in surveys - i.e. making up a sock puppet and asking them a question instead of a real person. The companies peddling this stuff claim it matches real surveys by over 90%. Well sure, it's easy enough to make up or guess the result of a lot of survey questions - the whole point of doing research is to find the 10% of surprising or interesting findings.

Nate Silver ✓
@NateSilver538

Using AI "respondents" is literally just making up fake data. Certainly not a poll by any reasonable definition. Firms that make up fake data are permabanned from Silver Bulletin averages and forecasts. There's no exception just because you used ChatGPT for your fake numbers.

👍👎❤️ 145

19 comments · 8 reposts

LinkedIn, March 24, 2026

Challenges in setting up synthetic users

- **Diversity** (Generic and stereotypical outputs that lack human diversity)
- **Bias** (Systematic inaccuracies when simulating human groups)
- **Sycophany** (Inaccuracies due to excessively userpleasing outputs)
- **Alienness** (Superficially accurate results generated by non-humanlike mechanisms)
- **Generalization** (Inaccuracies in out-of-distribution contexts, limiting scientific discovery)
- Models trained on **WEIRD** input
- Lack of variance, „correct answer“ bias
- Lack of **nomological complexity**
- **Effect exaggeration**
- **Reversed prospect theory**
- ...

Anthis, J. R., Liu, R., Richardson, S. M., Kozlowski, A. C., Koch, B., Evans, J., Brynjolfsson, E., & Bernstein, M. (2025). *LLM Social Simulations Are a Promising Research Method* (arXiv:2504.02234). arXiv. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2504.02234>

Abdurahman, S., Atari, M., Karimi-Malekabadi, F., Xue, M. J., Trager, J., Park, P. S., Golazizian, P., Omrani, A., & Dehghani, M. (2024). Perils and opportunities in using large language models in psychological research. *PNAS Nexus*, 3(7). <https://doi.org/10.1093/pnasnexus/pgae245>

Cui, Z., Li, N., & Zhou, H. (2025). A large-scale replication of scenario-based experiments in psychology and management using large language models. *Nature Computational Science*, 5(8), 627–634. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s43588-025-00840-7>

Xiao, F., & Wang, X. X. (2025). Evaluating the ability of large Language models to predict human social decisions. *Scientific Reports*, 15(1), 32290. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41598-025-17188-7>

Synthetic personas (examples)

Microsoft
Tiny Troupe

Simile.ai

Egoai.com

Agent
Society

Societies.io

Experial.de

Agenda

Three examples

Synthetic users
(quali): Tiny
Troupe

Streamlined
(quanti) process
with synthetic
users: Experial

In progress: Tiny Troupe

```
focus_group.create_focus_group()
```

```
DEBUG:tinytroupe:Adding agent Lisa Becker_1776090414 to the environment.  
DEBUG:tinytroupe:Adding agent Thomas Neumann_1776090415 to the environment.  
DEBUG:tinytroupe:Adding agent Susanne Klein_1776090415 to the environment.  
DEBUG:tinytroupe:Adding agent Christian Wagner_1776090415 to the environment.  
DEBUG:tinytroupe:Adding agent Laura Köhler_1776090415 to the environment.  
TinyWorld(name='Travel Focus Group bf845c70')
```

Ask for a specific destination

```
▶ focus_group.run_destination_discussion(destination='Algarve', persona_semantics_prompt=INTERPRETATION_PROMPT, num_rounds=1)
```

```
... DEBUG:tinytroupe:-----> Transaction: broadcast with args ("IMPORTANT: HOW TO USE YOUR PERSONA  
DEBUG:tinytroupe:[Travel Focus Group bf845c70] Broadcasting message: 'IMPORTANT: HOW TO USE YOUR PERSONA DATA
```

```
Each participant has a persona defined by structured fields.  
Interpret and use them as follows:
```

- country_of_residence: your current country of living; assume local norms, infrastructure, and travel constraints apply.
- travel_preferences: preferred types of holidays and activities; prioritize

In progress: Tiny Troupe

```
- {'action': {'type': 'THINK', 'content': "I should answer the moderator's questions in first person, e
DEBUG:tinytroupe:Will attempt to checkpoint simulation state after transaction execution.
Thomas Neumann_1776839188 acts: [THINK]
    > I should answer the moderator's questions in first person,
    > emphasising family needs and my travel preferences: relaxation,
    > pool/sea swimming, short excursions, some amusement-park time.
    > Mention concerns: travel time, heat, crowds, child facilities and
    > medical care. Say who I'd travel with (partner and two young
    > children) and the type of holiday (family-friendly resort or
    > rental, relaxed pace). Keep tone polite, practical, slightly
    > cautious (consistent with medium-high neuroticism).
DEBUG:tinytroupe:[Thomas Neumann_1776839188] Current episode event count: 3.
DEBUG:tinytroupe:[Thomas Neumann_1776839188] Cognitive state: {'goals': 'Respond clearly to the focus-g
DEBUG:tinytroupe:-----> Transaction: _update_cognitive_state with a
DEBUG:tinytroupe:[Thomas Neumann_1776839188] Retrieving relevant memories for contextual target: Curren
```

- {'action': {'type': 'TALK', 'content': 'From my point of view Algarve is quite attractive for a family holiday
DEBUG:tinytroupe:Will attempt to checkpoint simulation state after transaction execution.

Thomas Neumann_1776839188 acts: [TALK]

> From my point of view Algarve is quite attractive for a family
> holiday. What draws me is the combination of good beaches and
> hotels with pools – that fits exactly what we look for: time by the
> sea, plenty of swimming (both pool and sea) and easy, short
> excursions. My children enjoy simple things like paddling and water
> play, and there are also family attractions in the region (aquatic
> parks, small zoos/animal shows) that would suit the older child.
> My main concerns are practical: how long the travel takes from
> Bavaria, whether beaches and hotels are child-friendly (shallow
> water, lifeguards, shaded areas), and how crowded it gets in high
> season. With a toddler and a primary-school child I also worry
> about medical care nearby and whether the accommodation has baby
> equipment or family rooms. I would probably avoid the hottest,
> busiest weeks and prefer shoulder season if possible. The type of
> holiday we'd have is a relaxed family break – mostly pool and beach
> days for resting, with a couple of short excursions (scenic drives,
> small local towns, maybe a boat trip if it's safe with the little
> one). An occasional day at a water park or family attraction would
> be nice for variety. We like a comfortable, family-friendly resort
> or a holiday apartment close to facilities so we can keep things
> flexible. I would travel with my partner and our two children (one
> toddler and one child around primary-school age). As a manager I
> value work-life balance, so these trips are about rest and giving
> the kids a good experience rather than a packed sightseeing
> programme. Overall I'm positive about Algarve as a family
> destination, provided logistics and child facilities meet our
> needs.

DEBUG:tinytroupe:[Thomas Neumann_1776839188] Current episode event count: 4.

DEBUG:tinytroupe:[Thomas Neumann_1776839188] Cognitive state: {'goals': 'Respond clearly to the focus-group que

In progress: Tiny Troupe

```
- { action : { type : TALK , content : From my perspective the Algarve sounds very appealing because it  
DEBUG:tinytroupe:Will attempt to checkpoint simulation state after transaction execution.
```

```
Laura Köhler_1776839188 acts: [TALK]
```

```
> From my perspective the Algarve sounds very appealing because it  
> combines easy relaxation with nature and family-friendly activities.  
> I like wide beaches and clear sea for swimming, gentle coastal walks  
> and small excursions – exactly the kind of low-key outdoor things my  
> family enjoys. The warm, sunny weather and the chance to spend time  
> by the sea, go on short hikes and take the children on simple  
> excursions are what attract me most. My main concerns would be  
> practical: it can get very crowded in high season, which makes  
> relaxing with children harder; keeping the kids protected from the  
> sun; and watching costs for accommodation and outings. I also think  
> about travel time from Hesse and how to fit the trip around my part-  
> time work schedule and the children's school holidays. The type of  
> holiday I would choose is a family beach holiday with a relaxed  
> rhythm: a good base (an apartment or family-friendly hotel) where we  
> can cook sometimes, days at the beach or short boat trips, a couple  
> of local excursions to nature or small towns, and easy activities for  
> the children like swimming and gentle cycling or walking. I value  
> downtime as much as a bit of gentle sport. I would travel with my  
> partner and our children (the older one can help a bit with the  
> younger ones). We need something that suits ages roughly 6-17 –  
> things that keep teenagers entertained but are safe and simple for  
> the younger kids too. Overall, Algarve fits my priorities of family  
> time, nature, and a calm escape from routine, as long as we plan to  
> avoid the busiest weeks and take sensible precautions for the kids.
```

```
DEBUG:tinytroupe:[Laura Köhler_1776839188] Current episode event count: 4.
```

```
DEBUG:tinytroupe:[Laura Köhler_1776839188] Cognitive state: {'goals': 'Give a clear, persona-consistent op
```

```
DEBUG:tinytroupe:-----> Transaction: _update_cognitive_state with args
```

```
DEBUG:tinytroupe:[Laura Köhler_1776839188] Retrieving relevant memories for contextual target: Current Con
```

Research questions (together with Daniel Iglesias)

Three examples

Synthetic users
(quali): Tiny
Troupe

Streamlined
(quanti) process
with synthetic
users: Experial

In progress: Experial

We would like to survey 2,000 people aged 14 and over in Germany about their vacation travel. The survey will determine whether and how many trips respondents took in 2025, broken down into vacation trips of 5 days or more, short trips of 2-4 days, business trips with at least one overnight stay, and other trips with at least one overnight stay. The second question will explore what respondents consider most important when taking a vacation. A list of 29 items will be asked; the list is provided below. Here are the question wordings and answer options: Question 1: Did you undertake the following kinds of holiday trips in the past year, 2025? If yes, how many of those trips did you undertake approximately? 1 Holiday trips (more than 5 days duration) 2 Short trips (2 - 4 days duration) 3 Business trips with at least one overnight stay 4 Other trips with at least one overnight stay

Question 2: Let's talk about holidays. There are aspects about holidays that one would consider as more or less important. Please tell me which of these aspects are very important for you personally when you are on holiday. 1 Relaxation, no stress, no pressure 2 Freedom, free time 3 Get away from daily routine 4 Meet new people 5 New experiences, diversion from the ordinary, do a lot of different things 6 Be entertained 7 Do something cultural and educational 8 Spend time with people close to me (partner, family, children, friends) 9 Sports 10 Gentle sport or games/fitness 11 Rest, do nothing, be lazy 12 Meet the locals 13 Fun, amusement, enjoy myself 14 Recuperate 15 Do something for my health 16 Get to know other countries, see the world 17 Revisit an area, relive memories of a place 18 Spoil myself, treat myself to something 19 Get completely new impressions, discover something totally different 20 Travel around, be on the move 21 Share experiences, do something with nice people 22 Flirt, holiday romance, sex/erotic experience 23 Adventure, take risks, do something extraordinary 24 Do something for my appearance, get a tan, get a nice, healthy glow 25 Enjoy nature (beautiful scenery, clean air, clean water) 26 Healthy climate 27 Escape from pollution 28 Sun, warmth, good weather 29 Play with the children, spend time with them

Dirk Schmücker • Apr 20, 2026

In progress: Experial

 experial

Perfect! I'll start by defining a clear research goal based on your input and extract the target group parameters to guide the next steps.

Research Goal

Analyze the vacation travel behavior of people aged 14 and over in Germany in 2025 by quantifying the number and types of trips taken (vacation trips of 5 days or more, short trips of 2-4 days, business trips, and other overnight trips) and identifying the most important factors influencing their holiday decisions from a specified list of 29 aspects.

I'll now extract the target group parameters.

I have successfully extracted the target group parameters based on the research goal.

Based on the research goal you shared, I've put together a draft of your survey that aligns with the key insights you're aiming to uncover. Please review the questions and confirm before we proceed.

Survey

1. Which of the following types of trips have you personally participated in during the past 12 months? Please select all that apply. Multi select
 - Vacation trip (5 days or more)
 - Short trip (2-4 days)
 - Business trip
 - Other overnight trip

- Escape from pollution
- Sun, warmth, good weather
- Play with the children, spend time with them

7. What is your current age group?

Single select

- 14-19 years
- 20-29 years
- 30-39 years
- 40-49 years
- 50-59 years
- 60-69 years
- 70 years and older

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 experial

Virtual Panel

Faster, more cost-effective option, great for early testing or directional insights.

Human Panel

Provides rich, authentic insights and is ideal if you're looking for depth and nuance.

Hybrid Panel

Soon

Best of both worlds if you want to get a mix of authentic insights and twin generated insights.

Perfect! Now that we've clearly defined your research goal and crafted the survey questions, the next step is to start collecting responses. Let me know your preferred approach, and I can help guide you through setting it up effectively.

Large-scale modeling with 500 participants

Dirk Schmücker • Apr 20, 2026

 experial

You have chosen the option: Large-scale clustering or simulation (500 participants). I will continue with this option.

I'm now starting to create diverse respondent profiles, evaluating each for demographic and behavioral alignment with our target criteria. Profiles that don't meet the research objectives are flagged and

 [Creating diverse respondent profiles...](#)

 experial

You have chosen the option: Large-scale clustering or simulation (500 participants). I will continue with this option.

I'm now starting to create diverse respondent profiles, evaluating each for demographic and behavioral alignment with our target criteria. Profiles that don't meet the research objectives are flagged and replaced to ensure quality.

 [Compiling final panel...](#)

What can I research for you?

Dirk Schmücker • Apr 20, 2026

experial

You have chosen the option: Large-scale clustering or simulation (500 participants). I will continue with this option.

I'm now starting to create diverse respondent profiles, evaluating each for demographic and behavioral alignment with our target criteria. Profiles that don't meet the research objectives are flagged and replaced to ensure quality.

I'll begin interviewing each respondent using our prepared survey questions, I've organized the raw responses for each question separately—feel free to take a look while I continue.

☰ Which of the following types of trips have you personally participated in during the past 12 months? Please select all that apply.
Multi select

☰ How many vacation trips of 5 days or more did you take in the past 12 months?
Numerical

☰ How many short trips (2–4 days) did you take in the past 12 months?
Numerical

☰ How many business trips (of any length) did you take in the past 12 months?
Numerical

☰ How many other overnight trips (not business or vacation) did you take in the past 12 months?
Numerical

☰ Let's talk about holidays. There are aspects about holidays that one would consider as more or less important. Please tell me which of these aspects are very important for you personally when you are on holiday.
Multi select

☰ What is your current age group?
Single select

🔄 Interviewing Virtual Panel... (45%)

What can I research for you?

Survey responses

Which of the following types of trips have you personally participated in during the past 12 months? Please select all that apply.

ID	Answer
#1	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip
#2	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip
#3	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip
#4	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip
#5	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip
#6	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip
#7	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip
#8	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip
#9	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip
#10	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip
#11	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip
#12	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip
#13	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Short trip (2–4 days)
#14	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip
#15	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip

Showing 1-15 of 226

Sample comparison: Age group composition

Reference Sample

Synthetic Sample

Reiseanalyse 2026

- n = 7,000 face-to-face, random-route, next-birthday
- Dec 25-Feb 26
- Population definition: Germanspeaking, 14+ years, in private households

Experial synthetic sample

- n = 500
- April 2026

Sample comparison: Holiday trips 5+ days, 2025

Reference Sample

Synthetic Sample

Reiseanalyse 2026

- n = 7,000 face-to-face, random-route, next-birthday
- Dec 25-Feb 26
- Population definition: Germanspeaking, 14+ years, in private households

Experial synthetic sample

- n = 500
- April 2026

Also synthetic data need cleaning

	A	B	C	
1	Which of the following types of trips have you personally participated in during the past 12 months?	How many vacation trips of 5 days or more did you take in the past 12 months?	How many short trips (2–4 days) did you take in the past 12 months?	How many vacation trips of 5 days or more did you take in the past 12 months?
2	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	1	1	0
3	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	1	2	3
4	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	1	1	3
5	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Business trip	1	1	0
6	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	1	1	3
7	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip	0	0	0
8	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip	1	0	0
9	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	1	3	0
10	Short trip (2–4 days), Business trip	1	3	0
11	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Short trip (2–4 days), Business trip	1	1	3
12	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip	0	0	3
13	Short trip (2–4 days), Business trip, Other overnight trip	0	1	0
14	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	0	1	0
15	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	1	2	0
16	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	0	1	0
17	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip	0	4	0
18	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	0	0	0
19	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Short trip (2–4 days)	1	3	0
20	Short trip (2–4 days), Other overnight trip	1	2	0
21	Vacation trip (5 days or more), Other overnight trip	1	1	0

Holiday Travel Motives

Pearson $r = .535$
Spearman $Rho = .552$

Survey data collection process times

Total study cost: 30–50 €

Own estimate für 500 respondents, 5-10 questions

Productivity kills quality

Agenda

1

What consumer researchers did over the last 100 years or so

2

What happened since 2022

3

Three examples for the state of the play

4

What can be expected in the years to come?

Already there

Synthetic Data for LLM Training

 M Follow 6 min read · Jun 4, 2025

As LLMs grow, real-world data is running out — it's costly, limited, and legally complex. Synthetic data is emerging as a scalable, cheaper, and customizable alternative.

<https://medium.com/foundation-models-deep-dive/synthetic-data-for-llm-training-4c5b70371e04>, June 4, 2025

Probably to expect

Growing skills and abilities of generative AI

Lower requirements of data users in favour of lower cost per interview/per study

Advent of Generative Agents

Coming years

You are here

Overcome limitations of interviews & observations

- Real human's stated preferences do not necessarily reflect their real preferences
 - Biases
 - Lying (social desirability)
 - Using ChatGPT (!)
- Analogy: Autonomously driving cars are safer than human driven cars¹
- What if agents provide a more direct (correct?) way into the brains of consumers because they know so much about us?

1: Abdel-Aty, M., & Ding, S. (2024). A matched case-control analysis of autonomous vs human-driven vehicle accidents. *Nature Communications*, 15(1), 4931. <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-024-48526-4>

Coming years

You are here

Overcome limitations of human consumer behaviour

- So far, humans are the target of consumer research, either directly or indirectly.
- That makes sense because humans make buying decisions
- But what if they don't? What if agents act only on behalf of humans, but not necessarily like humans?
- Let agents do the job and ignore the humans.

Gibberlink example: Anton Pidkuiko: Two AI agents on a phone call realize they're both AI and switch to a superior audio signal ggwave, 23 Feb 2025, <https://www.youtube.com/watch?v=EtNagNezo8w>

Conclusions

- Synthetic respondents have the potential to change the fundamental paradigm of consumer research
- In quantitative research, synthetic samples seem to be far from being a valid replacement for human samples
- In qualitative research, synthetic respondents produce plausible, but stereotypical answers.
- However, three developments might serve as future enablers for this technology
 - Growing skills and abilities of generative AI
 - Lower requirements of data users in favour of lower cost per interview/per study
 - Generative Agents might replace the need to struggle with humans because agents know humans better than they do or take decisions on behalf of humans
- The research field is relatively new and dynamic and hard to predict.

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